

Report from Uvejs Rrudhani about

The advantage of Laplace transformation to “the normal” solution for total differential

Essentials of total differential

At first for what we need the total differential? When we would like to plot a graph from a normal electricity wave we need a lot of variables. Remember the normal x^2 function. When we plot the function we will become a simple graph.

[1]

When we look now for an example the discharge process of a condenser it is impossible to describe this kind of a function with 'normal' variables. Look at the examples.

[2]

Another example is the control techniques. The description of the control is only possible with total differential. On this point it will be too difficult to explain in detail why. For more information I am referring to literature.

Now the advantages between the two. On the examples we see the same task with two different kinds of solution. The first one will be a very easy Exercise because we have only a function without an inhomogeneous part. In especially the inhomogeneous part of the function makes the total differential very complicated. The first step is always the same. At first it must

to solve the homogeny part. After the solution of the homogeny part it must be approach the right solution with the help of tables of the inhomogeneous part.

$p_n(x)$	$(\alpha = 0, \beta = 0)$	$q_n(x)$
$p_n(x) \cos(\beta x)$	$(\alpha = 0)$	$q_n(x) \cos(\beta x) + r_n(x) \sin(\beta x)$
$p_n(x) \sin(\beta x)$	$(\alpha = 0)$	$q_n(x) \cos(\beta x) + r_n(x) \sin(\beta x)$
$p_n(x)e^{\alpha x}$	$(\beta = 0)$	$q_n(x)e^{\alpha x}$
$e^{\alpha x} \cos(\beta x)$	$(p_0(x) = 1)$	$ae^{\alpha x} \cos(\beta x) + be^{\alpha x} \sin(\beta x)$
$e^{\alpha x} \sin(\beta x)$	$(p_0(x) = 1)$	$ae^{\alpha x} \cos(\beta x) + be^{\alpha x} \sin(\beta x)$
$p_n(x)e^{\alpha x} \cos(\beta x)$		$q_n(x)e^{\alpha x} \cos(\beta x) + r_n(x)e^{\alpha x} \sin(\beta x)$
$p_n(x)e^{\alpha x} \sin(\beta x)$		$q_n(x)e^{\alpha x} \cos(\beta x) + r_n(x)e^{\alpha x} \sin(\beta x)$

[3]

In the examples the first one do not have an inhomogeneous part. The inhomogeneous part in this case is zero and because of that we do not need to approach the solution. In the second example we must approach a solution of the inhomogeneous part because it is not zero. When we look in detail the two examples we will realize the big advantage of Laplace.

In the Laplace transformation it is not important if we have an inhomogeneous part or not. We never need to approach a solution. The only thing what we need to do is to transform the normal variable in 'Laplace variable'. For that we need tables too but it is definitely easier to transform the variables then to approach an inhomogeneous solution. A small part of the Laplace tables we see now.

$f(t)$	$F(s) = \mathcal{L}\{f(t)\}$
1	$\frac{1}{s}$
t^n	$\frac{n!}{s^{n+1}}$
$e^{\alpha t}$	$\frac{1}{s - \alpha}$
$t^n e^{\alpha t}$	$\frac{n!}{(s - \alpha)^{n+1}}$
$\cos \beta t$	$\frac{s}{s^2 + \beta^2}$
$\sin \beta t$	$\frac{\beta}{s^2 + \beta^2}$
$e^{\alpha t} \cos \beta t$	$\frac{s - \alpha}{(s - \alpha)^2 + \beta^2}$

$f(t)$	$F(s) = \mathcal{L}\{f(t)\}$
$e^{\alpha t} \sin \beta t$	$\frac{\beta}{(s - \alpha)^2 + \beta^2}$
$\cosh \beta t$	$\frac{s}{s^2 - \beta^2}$
$\sinh \beta t$	$\frac{\beta}{s^2 - \beta^2}$
$e^{\alpha t} \cosh \beta t$	$\frac{s - \alpha}{(s - \alpha)^2 - \beta^2}$
$e^{\alpha t} \sinh \beta t$	$\frac{\beta}{(s - \alpha)^2 - \beta^2}$
$\frac{e^{\beta t} - e^{\alpha t}}{\beta - \alpha}$	$\frac{1}{(s - \alpha)(s - \beta)}$
$\frac{\beta e^{\beta t} - \alpha e^{\alpha t}}{\beta - \alpha}$	$\frac{s}{(s - \alpha)(s - \beta)}$

[4]

On the following pages I will show now the 2 examples with the two different methods to solve.

Solution with normal methods (without inhomogeneous part)

$$2a) \quad y'' + 1,5y' - y = 0 \quad ; \quad y(0) = 2 \quad ; \quad y'(0) = 6$$

Linear total differential, homogen

① charakteristik polynom (homogen part)

$$\lambda^2 + 1,5\lambda - 1 = 0$$

$$\lambda_{1,2} = -\frac{3}{4} \pm \sqrt{\frac{9}{16} + 1} = -\frac{3}{4} \pm \sqrt{\frac{25}{16}} = -\frac{3}{4} \pm \frac{5}{4}$$

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \rightarrow \lambda_1 = 1/2 \\ \rightarrow \lambda_2 = -2 \end{array} \right\}$$

Case 1: Solve of Homogene part

$$y_h = C_1 \cdot e^{\frac{1}{2}x} + C_2 \cdot e^{-2x}$$

② Für spezielle Lösung $y(0) = 2$, $y'(0) = 6$

$$y'(x) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot C_1 \cdot e^{\frac{1}{2}x} - 2 \cdot C_2 \cdot e^{-2x}$$

$$y'(0) = 6 \Rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \cdot C_1 \cdot \underbrace{e^{\frac{1}{2} \cdot 0}}_{=1} - 2 \cdot C_2 \cdot \underbrace{e^{-2 \cdot 0}}_{=1} = 6$$

$$\frac{1}{2} C_1 - 2 C_2 = 6 \quad | \cdot 2$$

$$C_1 - 4 C_2 = 12$$

$$C_1 = 12 + 4 C_2$$

$$y(0) = 2 \Rightarrow C_1 \cdot \underbrace{e^{\frac{1}{2} \cdot 0}}_{=1} + C_2 \cdot \underbrace{e^{-2 \cdot 0}}_{=1} = 2$$

$$C_1 + C_2 = 2$$

$$C_2 = 2 - C_1$$

$$C_1 = 12 + 4 \cdot (2 - C_1) = \frac{12+8}{20} - 4 C_1$$

$$5 C_1 = 20 \Rightarrow C_1 = \frac{20}{5} = 4$$

$$C_2 = 2 - C_1 = 2 - 4 = -2$$

$$\text{Also } C_1 = 4 \\ C_2 = -2$$

$$y(x) = 4 \cdot e^{\frac{1}{2}x} - 2 \cdot e^{-2x}$$

Solution with Laplace (without inhomogeneous part)

$$y'' + 1.5 * y' - y = 0 ; y(0) = 2 ; y'(0) = 6$$

$$s^2 y(s) - sy(0) - y'(0) + 1.5[sy(s) - y(0)] - y(s) = 0$$

$$y(s)[s^2 + 1.5s - 1] = 2s + 9$$

$$y(s) = \frac{2s+9}{s^2 + 1.5s - 1}$$

$$\text{with p-q formula } s_{1,2} = \frac{-p}{2} \pm \sqrt{\left(\frac{-p}{2}\right)^2 - q} \text{ and } s^2 + 1.5s - 1 = 0$$

$$s_{1,2} = \frac{-3}{4} \pm \sqrt{\frac{9}{16} + 1}$$

$$s_1 = 0.5$$

$$s_2 = -2 ; \text{ hence with partial fraction}$$

$$y(s) = \frac{2s+9}{(s+2)(s-0.5)} = \frac{A}{s+2} + \frac{B}{s-0.5}$$

Definition coefficients A and B

$$2s+9 = A(s-0.5) + B(s+2)$$

$$\text{If } s = -2 \text{ then } A = -2$$

$$\text{If } s = 0.5 \text{ then } B = 4 \text{ therefore}$$

$$y(s) = \frac{-2}{s+2} + \frac{4}{s-0.5} ;$$

Back transformation from Laplace to normal

With Laplace transformation $\frac{1}{s-\alpha}$ equal with $e^{\alpha t}$

$$L^{-1}(y(s)) = 4e^{0.5t} - 2e^{-2t}$$

Solution with normal methods (with inhomogeneous part)

ix) $y' - 4y = -5 \cdot e^{4x}, y(0) = 2$

inhomogeneous total differential with constant coefficients

① Solve the homogene part

$$y' - 4y = 0$$

$$\lambda - 4 = 0 \rightarrow \lambda = 4$$

$$y_h = C \cdot e^{4x}$$

② Find out approach solution for

a)

$$g(x) = -5 \cdot e^{4x}$$

$$\lambda = 4$$

and

$$e^{4x}$$

Same zero points

4 too

$$y_p = A \cdot x \cdot e^{4x}$$

b) Differentiation from y_p to x

$$y_p' = 4 \cdot A \cdot x \cdot e^{4x} + A \cdot e^{4x}$$

c) Fill in y_p and y_p' in origin formula

$$y' - 4y = -5 \cdot e^{4x}$$

$$4 \cdot A \cdot x \cdot e^{4x} + A \cdot e^{4x} + 4(A \cdot x \cdot e^{4x}) = -5 \cdot e^{4x}$$

$$A \cdot e^{4x} = -5 \cdot e^{4x} \Rightarrow A = -5$$

$$y_p = -5 \cdot x \cdot e^{4x}$$

③ $y = y_h + y_p$

$$y = C \cdot e^{4x} - 5 \cdot x \cdot e^{4x}$$

④ Special solution for $y(0) = 2$

$$C \cdot e^{4 \cdot 0} - 5 \cdot 0 \cdot e^{4 \cdot 0} = 2 \Rightarrow C = 2$$

$$y = 2 \cdot e^{4x} - 5 \cdot x \cdot e^{4x}$$

Solution with Laplace (with inhomogeneous part)

$$y' - 4y = -5e^{4t}; \quad y(0) = 2;$$

$$sy(s) - y(0) - 4y(s) = -5 \frac{1}{s-4}$$

$$y(s)[s-4] = \frac{2(s-4)-5}{s-4}$$

$$y(s) = \frac{2(s-4)-5}{(s-4)^2} = \frac{A}{(s-4)^2} + \frac{B}{(s-4)}$$

Definition coefficients A and B

$$y(s) = 2(s-4) - 5 = A + B(s-4)$$

$$\text{if } s = 4 \text{ then } A = -5$$

$$\text{If } s = 0 \text{ then } B = 2$$

$$Y(s) = \frac{-5}{(s-4)^2} + \frac{2}{(s-4)}$$

Back transformation from Laplace to normal

With Laplace transformation $\frac{1}{s-\alpha}$ equal with $e^{\alpha t}$ and $\frac{n!}{(s-\alpha)^{n+1}}$ equal with $t^n e^{\alpha t}$

$$L^{-1}(Y(s)) = 2e^{4t} - 5te^{4t}$$

Words 655

Sources

[1] <http://uni-wiki.mayastudios.net/images/f/fd/X-quadrat.png>

[2] <http://www.g-hoehne.de/ELEKTR/EL19-D/image008.jpg>

[3, 4, 5] Tutorial notice from Prof. Dr. Andreas Bolsch, MNI, Fachhochschule Giessen-Friedberg, University of applied science

Notice source 3: Only the Exercises are from Prof. Dr. Bolsch. The solution is completely from me